

Building Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation from 2 to 260 GHz

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Abstract — This paper analyzes the frequency-dependent electromagnetic characteristics of usual flat-surface low-loss building materials. Reflection and transmission losses are measured from 2 to 260 GHz and the related permittivity and conductivity are estimated. Results are in agreement with the ITU-R P2040-3 model that is mainly defined for frequency below 100 GHz. The permittivity can be modelled by a constant value and the conductivity can be modelled by a frequency-dependent function equal to af^b . Some differences between the measured and simulated transmission losses have been observed for composite materials that can no longer be considered as homogeneous for frequency above 50 GHz.

Keywords — material conductivity, material permittivity, reflection loss, transmission loss, millimeter wave

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical models such as ray tracing or ray launching models [1] use a geographical database to compute all possible paths (direct, reflected, diffracted, diffused paths) between two or more points such as transmitter, receiver, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, relay, etc. These models are consequently frequently used for the performance evaluation of wireless radio interfaces. The path amplitude is given by physical laws according to the interaction type between the electromagnetic (EM) wave and the environment. This paper focuses on the reflection and transmission losses experienced by the EM wave when reflected by a surface or transmitted through a material. For smooth surface and homogeneous materials, reflection and transmission coefficients depend on the incidence angle, the wave polarization and the material permittivity and conductivity. The goal of this paper is to discuss the permittivity and conductivity material frequency dependency. The analysis is based on contiguous material reflection and transmission loss measurements from 2 to 260 GHz. This work extends previous work from the same authors presented in [2][3] by including new materials, estimating the permittivity and conductivity and pushing the upper frequency limit up to 260 GHz. More details regarding the theoretical model, the data processing, the measurement results and a literature review on material characteristics in millimeter wave can be found in [4][5].

II. THEORETICAL MODEL

In usual human environments, EM waves travel from a transmitter to a receiver located in the air and interact with building materials that are considered as homogeneous isotropic low-loss dielectrics. Building materials are usually represented by a smooth-surface slab with thickness d as

indicated in Fig. 1. The slab may be a glass window, concrete wall, plasterboard partition wall, etc. Fig. 1 illustrates the different paths created by the interaction between the EM wave and the slab. As the wave reaches the first material interface, a part of the wave is reflected, and the rest is transmitted through the material. The transmitted part from the first material interface penetrates through the material, and it is attenuated due to the penetration loss. Arriving to the second interface, a part of the wave will be transmitted, and the rest will be reflected. Likewise, multiple reflections are created inside the slab. In the following, for the sake of simplicity, only transmitted paths 1 and 2 (named 1T and 2T) and reflected paths 1 and 2 (named 1R and 2R) will be considered, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Let's define μ_0 and ε_0 the vacuum permeability and permittivity respectively, and ε_r and σ the slab relative permittivity and conductivity, respectively. We denote $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ the frequency-dependent reflection and transmission Transfer Functions (TF) of the material slab whereas r and t are the reflection and transmission TF at the air-dielectric interface. p is the penetration TF inside the material. $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ are analytically defined in Fig. 1. r , t , ε_r and σ are potentially frequency-dependent, but for clarity reasons, it does not appear in the equations.

Fig. 1. $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ definition at normal incidence

III. MEASUREMENT SETUP

The measurement equipment is based on a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) and frequency extenders that can measure S parameters from 2 to 260 GHz. The measurement is divided into contiguous sub-bands defined by the frequency limits of the VNA, extenders, or antennas (2-30 GHz, 30-50 GHz, 50-75 GHz, 75-110 GHz, 110-170 GHz, 170-260 GHz). Antennas are dual-ridge Ultra-Wideband antennas for frequencies below 50 GHz and standard horn pyramidal antennas for frequencies

above 50 GHz. Fig. 2 illustrates the mechanical part that allows a free space measurement for both transmission and reflection. The material under test was placed at normal incidence between the two antennas in the material holder center. Materials investigated in this paper are common building materials. Polymere Fiber Board (PFB) is a vegetable fiber-reinforced polymere composite material and is used in many office objects. Medium Density Fiberboard (MDF) is a compressed wood fiber board and as the same functions as PFB. Gypsum Fiber Board (GFB) is a vegetable fiber-reinforced gypsum material and may be used for partition walls or for the floor. The mortar sample is a home-made sample with a surface as smooth as possible.

Fig. 2. Measurement setup and measured materials

For each frequency sub-band, the material measurement is preceded by two reference measurements, one in free space the other with a metallic plate inserting into the material holder. We note $S_{11}^{FS}(f)$ and $S_{21}^{FS}(f)$ the S parameters measured by the VNA in free space and $S_{11}^{Met}(f)$ the S_{11} parameter measured with the metallic plate. When reference measurements are completed, slabs are put in the material holder and material measurements are proceeded. The measurement is performed at 3 points (Pt_i , $i=1..3$) separated by 10 cm as illustrated by Fig. 2. The raw material measurements are denoted by $S_{11}^{Meas}(f)$ and $S_{21}^{Meas}(f)$ for reflection and transmission measurements, respectively. We denote by $H_r^{Mut}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mut}(f)$ the intrinsic material reflection and transmission TF. They are computed according to (1)

$$H_r^{MUT}(f) = \frac{TG[S_{11}^{Meas}(f) - S_{11}^{FS}(f)]}{TG[S_{11}^{Met}(f) - S_{11}^{FS}(f)]} \quad H_t^{MUT}(f) = \frac{TG[S_{21}^{Meas}(f)]}{TG[S_{21}^{FS}(f)]} \quad (1)$$

$TG[.]$ is the time gating operator. It is a temporal filter applied on the iFFT of S parameters that rejects all undesirable components such as wall reflections or material edge diffractions. We define $h_r^{Mut}(t)$ and $h_t^{Mut}(t)$ the inverse Fourier Transform of $H_r^{Mut}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mut}(f)$. In the following sections, the data analysis and model comparison will be mainly based on power profiles. A pp prefix added to a complex vector indicates the vector power profile. For instance, $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ is the power profile of $H_r^{Mut}(f)$ and is equal to $10\text{Log}_{10}(|H_r^{Mut}(f)|^2)$.

IV. DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

As the measurement presented in this work are complex measurement over very large bandwidths, it is possible to resolve in the time domain the multipath described in the theoretical part. For instance, Fig. 3 shows $pp_{h_r^{Mut}}(t)$ for GFB.

Path 1R and 2R can be clearly identified. Consequently, we apply separate estimation methods for the permittivity and conductivity. First, the permittivity is estimated by two different methods based either on the delay of transmitted paths or on the amplitude of reflected paths. We will only consider path 1R amplitude and path 1T delay as illustrated in Fig. 3 because second order paths are often below the noise level at the highest frequencies. The initial measurement subbands were slightly rearranged to define nine new subbands of about 30 GHz bandwidth (2-30 GHz, 30-50 GHz, 50-75 GHz, 75-110 GHz, 110-140 GHz, 140-170 GHz, 170-200 GHz, 200-230 GHz, 230-260 GHz). An analyzed bandwidth of roughly 30 GHz is a good trade-off to keep a good resolution for the path detection regarding the slabs thickness, to consider a constant value for the permittivity and to assess the large-scale permittivity frequency dependency.

Fig. 3. Permittivity estimation method

Method 1 is based on the delay. Let's define t_{p1T} the delay of path 1T, c the wave velocity in vacuum, v the wave celerity in material. ϵ_r is calculated as expressed in (2)

$$v = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} = \frac{d}{t_{p1T} + d/c} \Rightarrow \epsilon_r = \left(\frac{t_{p1T} * c}{d} + 1 \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Method 2 is based on the amplitude. Let's define h_r^{1R} the amplitude of path 1R. ϵ_r can be calculated as in (3).

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon_r} - 1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r} + 1} \Rightarrow \epsilon_r = \left(\frac{1+r}{1-r} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4. Permittivity estimation

Figure 4 shows the material relative permittivity averaged on the three measurement points and estimated by both methods. It can be observed that the permittivity estimated by both methods are slightly different for some materials. Nevertheless, estimated values from both methods do not highlight any dependence with the frequency. It confirms and

extends for frequencies up to 260 GHz the ITU recommendation P.2040-3 [6] that proposes a constant permittivity value regardless the frequency. The mortar results illustrate the estimation limits. No permittivity was estimated by method 1 above 170 GHz (subband 7 and above) as path 1T is highly attenuated and not resolved enough compared to the diffuse components generated inside the material. Permittivity estimated by method 2 is biased by the scattering due to the rough surface. The wave power reflected in the specular direction is diminished as a portion of the incident wave is reradiated in various scattered directions [7]. This point is currently under investigation and will be discussed in a future publication. The final permittivity value is averaged over the different frequency bands and both estimation methods.

The conductivity estimation was not performed by detecting path 1T amplitude for each frequency subband as the conductivity decreases with frequency and as the transmission losses are highly impacted by the material inhomogeneity as illustrated by Fig. 7. A simple approach was to consider the conductivity model given by the ITU-R recommendation P.2040-3 that expresses the frequency-dependent conductivity σ as $\sigma = af^b$, f being the frequency, a and b being two parameters depending on the material. a and b were fitted on the measurement by an iterative approach in order to minimize the error between $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ and $pp_{H_r^{ITUF}}(f)$. $H_r^{ITUF}(f)$ and $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ are TFs $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ described in section II applying the permittivity and conductivity model described in this section. This model is called ITUF as it is based on the ITU-R P.2040-3 theoretical framework but with parameters fitted on the measurement presented in this paper. Fig. 5 illustrates the conductivity frequency dependency by plotting the attenuation rate equal to $0.2 * \text{Log}_{10} \left(e^{\frac{\sigma}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r}}} \right)$ when expressed in dB/cm.

Fig. 5. Material attenuation rate

Figures 6 and 7 compare $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ with $pp_{H_r^{ITUF}}(f)$ and $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ with $pp_{H_r^{ITUF}}(f)$, respectively. $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ are well fitted by the ITUF model, even at frequencies above 100 GHz. We clearly observe in Fig. 7 the regular periodic small-scale fading due to the complex recombination between path 1R and path 2R. When the frequency increases, the amplitude of path 2R decreases and $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ tends to r . No significant difference is observed between the three measurement points except for the mortar. This effect is due to the scattering on the surface [7]. The fading is no more due to the complex recombination between path 1R and path 2R but is due to the complex recombination of scattered components.

The analysis of transmission results leads to similar conclusions. The frequency-dependent conductivity can be well modeled by the ITUF model “on average”. Nevertheless, the absolute difference between $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ and $pp_{H_r^{ITUF}}(f)$ may exceed 10 dB for frequencies above 100 GHz. It suggests that diffuse scattered components are created inside the material due to the material inhomogeneity and interfere with path 1T. When the diffuse component is the most significant component, the ITUF model may become inaccurate. For instance, the ITUF model overestimates the attenuation rate for mortar with frequency above 150 GHz. For wireless communication applications, this model inaccuracy may not be a concern as material with a high attenuation rate of about several tens dB/cm may be considered as a blocker.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper shows that the investigated building materials permittivity ϵ_r does not change with the frequency in the frequency range [2-260 GHz] and that the conductivity σ can be simply modeled by the function af^b . The analysis was conducted on non-coated flat-surface material. Future work will focus on the impact of the material surface state. Reflection coefficients on rough, relief and coated surfaces will be measured and compare with the theoretical value given by the permittivity.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partly funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe/JU SNS project Hexa-X-II (Grant Agreement no. 101095759). The authors would like to thank all people and especially Eric Seguenot from the CREMANT laboratory (joint laboratory between Orange Labs and Univ. Côte d’Azur) for their help and support during the measurement campaigns.

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Fig. 6. Comparison $pp_H r^{Mut}(f)$ and $pp_H r^{ITUF}(f)$: Mortar (a), PFB (b), GFB (c), Ceramic (d), laminated glass (e), MDF(f).¹

Fig. 7. Comparison $pp_H t^{Mut}(f)$ and $pp_H t^{ITUF}(f)$: Mortar (a), PFB (b), GFB (c), Ceramic (d), Laminated glass (e), MDF(f).²

^{1,2}The triplet (ϵ_r, a, b) inserted after the following material names indicates the parameters estimated from the measurement and used for the ITUF model: Mortar (4.6, 0.002, 1.5), PFB (1.7, 0.0001, 1.55), GFB (3.5, 0.002, 1.25), ceramic (5.8, 0.005, 1.2), glass (6.3, 0.005, 1.2), MDF (2.05, 0.005, 1)